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Factores socioeconómicos que condicionan la motivación y el crecimiento profesional del profesorado universitario

Roman Oleksenko¹, Vlada Bilohur², Oleksandr Nepsha³,
Svitlana Hryshko⁴, Halyna Matviienko⁵

¹Volodymyr Vynnychenko Central Ukrainian State University, Kropyvnytskyi, Ukraine.
E-mail: roman.xdsl@ukr.net; ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2171-514X>

²Uzhhorod National University, Uzhhorod, Ukraine.

E-mail: bilovlada@gmail.com; ORCID iD: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1053-2716>

³Bogdan Khmelnytsky Melitopol State Pedagogical University, Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine.

E-mail: nepsha_aleks@ukr.net; ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-3929-9946>

⁴Bogdan Khmelnytsky Melitopol State Pedagogical University, Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine.

E-mail: gryshko245@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5054-3893>

⁵V.I. Vernadsky Taurida National University, Kyiv, Ukraine.

E-mail: halyna.matviienko@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5265-8379>

Resumen. El objetivo de este estudio fue examinar los factores socioeconómicos que influyen en la motivación de los profesores universitarios en sus actividades profesionales. El estudio también analizó los mecanismos y estrategias para incrementar la motivación docente con foco en mejorar su efectividad, satisfacción laboral y desarrollo profesional. El estudio utilizó un enfoque analítico, análisis funcional-estructural, análisis comparativo, evaluación de expertos y métodos de recomendaciones prácticas para recopilar y analizar datos. Basándose en una revisión de la literatura y datos empíricos, el estudio identificó estrategias clave para mejorar la motivación del personal docente, entre ellas: ofrecer salarios competitivos que sean acordes a las cualificaciones y la carga de trabajo; la introducción de diversas formas de incentivos financieros, como bonificaciones por publicación, becas de investigación, remuneración basada en la antigüedad y bonificaciones relacionadas con la acreditación; Fomentar la motivación no monetaria a través de oportunidades de avance profesional, premios formales, acceso a programas de desarrollo profesional y recursos académicos; crear un entorno social favorable a través de iniciativas de intercambio, programas de investigación financiados por la universidad y cooperación intrainstitucional; mejorar las condiciones de trabajo

mediante la modernización de las aulas y los laboratorios y la provisión de zonas de descanso cómodas; y la introducción de modelos de empleo flexibles que permitan al profesorado combinar actividades de docencia e investigación. Se espera que la implementación de estas medidas aumente la competitividad de la universidad, reduzca la rotación de personal y cree condiciones favorables para el crecimiento profesional del personal investigador y docente.

Palabras clave: motivación del profesorado universitario, institución de educación superior, motivación financiera, motivación no financiera, motivación social.

Socio-economic factors shaping the motivation and professional growth of university faculty

Abstract. The purpose of this study was to examine the socio-economic factors influencing the motivation of university faculty in their professional activities. The study also analyzed mechanisms and strategies for enhancing faculty motivation, with a focus on improving their effectiveness, job satisfaction, and professional development. To collect and analyze data, the study employed an analytical approach, functional-structural analysis, comparative analysis, expert evaluation, and practical recommendation methods. Based on a review of literature and empirical data, the study identified key strategies for enhancing faculty motivation, including: ensuring a competitive salary aligned with qualifications and workload; introducing various forms of financial incentives such as publication bonuses, research grants, seniority-based pay, and accreditation-related bonuses; promoting non-monetary motivation through career advancement opportunities, official awards, access to professional development programs, and academic resources; fostering a supportive social environment through experience-sharing initiatives, university-funded research programs, and intra-institutional collaboration; improving working conditions by modernizing classrooms, laboratories, and providing comfortable rest areas; and implementing flexible employment models that allow faculty to balance teaching and research activities. The implementation of these measures is expected to enhance university competitiveness, reduce faculty turnover, and create favorable conditions for the professional growth of academic staff.

Keywords: University faculty motivation, higher education institution, financial motivation, non-financial motivation, social motivation.

INTRODUCTION

The motivation of university faculty plays a crucial role in improving their productivity, fostering professional growth, and enhancing the quality of the discipline curriculum. Properly motivated university faculty are more committed to lesson preparation, which, in turn, positively influences the professional training of students (Tomashév's'ka, 2023). A significant factor in increasing faculty motivation is the encouragement of research and scientific activities (Altamirano, 2024). Participation in research projects not only fosters interest in securing research grants through competitive tenders but also boosts faculty members' publication activity and their engagement in academic conferences.

Enhancing faculty motivation helps address the issue of high staff turnover, increases job satisfaction, and fosters a stable academic workforce by ensuring continuity within university teams (Samborska et al., 2023). Well-motivated faculty also contribute to building a positive institutional reputation, which, in turn, attracts prospective students (Rubia et al., 2023).

A motivated academic workforce fosters a creative work environment and promotes a supportive and collaborative atmosphere within the institution (Urdabayev et al., 2024). Effective motivation strategies also enhance the competitiveness of the educational services offered by universities.

In their research, authors (Sindisiwe et al., 2023) identify several key types of employee motivation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Types of employee motivation in an organization

Source: Compiled according to Sindisiwe et al., 2023.

Financial motivation for university faculty should include fair and competitive compensation that corresponds to their workload, as well as various bonuses and incentives for publishing scientific papers, securing research grants, and implementing research projects (Samko, 2023). Additional financial incentives may include seniority-based salary increments, financial assistance for personal or family-related circumstances, as well as reimbursement for transportation costs and housing expenses (Puja et al., 2023).

Non-financial motivation for university faculty includes opportunities for career advancement, official recognition and awards, access to research fellowships, and participation in scientific conferences. Additionally, creating a comfortable working environment, fostering conditions for creative self-fulfillment, and ensuring institutional support for faculty members' professional responsibilities are essential factors in non-financial motivation (Venkatesh et al 2023).

Social motivation in the workplace may involve organizing corporate events to foster team cohesion, facilitating participation in pension programs and health insurance plans, and providing wellness support for employees and their families.

Intrinsic motivation among university faculty includes personal satisfaction derived from fulfilling professional responsibilities, opportunities to participate in cutting-edge research projects, creative self-actualization, and the societal prestige associated with the academic profession (Venkatesh et al., 2021).

Extrinsic motivation factors include individual performance evaluation by university leadership, public recognition, and the availability of well-equipped workspaces (Kerry et al., 2021).

According to Tabachuk (2022), several key factors contribute to the demotivation of university faculty (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Factors contributing to the demotivation of university faculty

Source: Compiled according to Tabachuk, 2022.

Increasing societal and student expectations of universities, which often cannot be met due to limited financial resources, have a negative impact on faculty motivation (Wilson, 2024). Additionally, competition among universities in the higher education market, along with the opportunity for faculty to secure employment in business sectors offering more attractive salaries and working conditions, further diminishes university instructors' motivation.

ANALYSIS OF RECENT RESEARCH AND PUBLICATIONS

Motivation plays a crucial role in enhancing faculty productivity, influencing both teaching quality and research output. Tomashevs'ka (2023) emphasizes the need for structured motivation management strategies in academic institutions, which can be extended to higher education settings. Her study identifies motivation as a critical factor for sustaining faculty engagement and improving institutional performance. Similarly, Samko (2023) analyzes the theoretical foundations of self-educational activities among faculty, underscoring the importance of continuous professional development in maintaining high teaching standards. A broader perspective on faculty motivation is provided by Tiwari & Chatterjee (2021), who explore how motivation affects individual productivity levels among teaching staff in private higher education institutions in India. Their findings suggest that a balanced approach, incorporating both financial and non-financial incentives, is essential for sustaining faculty motivation.

Several researchers emphasize the role of financial incentives in improving faculty motivation. Altamirano (2024) discusses the challenges faced by U.S. higher education institutions in a post-pandemic environment, particularly highlighting the need for competitive salaries and research funding to retain academic talent. In contrast, Puja & Chatterjee (2021) examine the impact of

financial motivation on faculty productivity, noting that salary structures, research grants, and performance-based incentives significantly contribute to academic engagement.

Beyond monetary rewards, Venkatesh (2023) explores job enrichment strategies as a non-financial motivational tool, demonstrating how enhanced job roles, professional autonomy, and leadership opportunities can lead to higher faculty satisfaction. The influence of institutional leadership and governance on faculty motivation has been widely studied. Rubia et al. (2023) examine transformational leadership styles in higher education institutions, concluding that effective leadership fosters greater organizational commitment and faculty motivation. Similarly, Kerry et al. (2023) explore how knowledge-sharing motivation and management support contribute to faculty engagement, emphasizing the importance of collaborative academic cultures.

METHODS

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative research methods to analyze faculty motivation in higher education institutions. The research design is structured to examine key motivational factors and their impact on the productivity, job satisfaction, and professional development of university faculty members.

Research Design

The study follows an analytical and comparative research design, utilizing multiple methodologies to assess faculty motivation strategies. The primary methods include:

- 1) Analytical Method – A comprehensive review of literature sources related to faculty motivation in higher education was conducted. This included both theoretical models and empirical studies from international and domestic contexts to identify key motivational mechanisms and their effectiveness.
- 2) Functional-Structural Method – Faculty motivation was analyzed as a complex system composed of interconnected elements. The study categorized motivational factors based on intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, material and non-material incentives, and strategies to assess their collective impact.
- 3) Comparative Analysis – The study compared various approaches to faculty motivation across different higher education institutions globally. Best practices from leading universities were examined to determine effective models for improving faculty motivation and retention.
- 4) Expert Evaluation Method – Faculty and administrative personnel from two universities were surveyed and interviewed to assess motivation factors, barriers, and possible improvements in academic motivation strategies.
- 5) Survey Methodology – A structured questionnaire was developed to collect quantitative data from university faculty regarding their motivation, job satisfaction, and professional development opportunities. The survey focused on financial incentives, career advancement, work environment, and institutional support. Responses were analyzed using statistical methods, including descriptive and inferential analysis, to identify patterns and relationships between different motivational factors.

By utilizing a comprehensive methodological approach, this study aims to provide data-driven recommendations for enhancing faculty motivation strategies in higher education institutions. The results will contribute to improving faculty retention, productivity, and the overall quality of academic institutions.

Survey for assessing faculty motivation in professional activities:

Section 1: General Information

What is your age?

- Under 30 years
- 30–40 years
- 41–50 years
- Over 50 years

How many years have you worked in higher education?

- Less than 5 years
- 5–10 years
- 11–20 years
- More than 20 years

What is your current position?

- Assistant Lecturer
- Senior Lecturer
- Associate Professor
- Full Professor
- Administrative Role

What type of institution do you work at?

- Public university
- Private university
- Research institute
- Other (please specify)

How would you describe your current workload?

- Too low
- Moderate
- High
- Too high

How often do you work beyond your official working hours?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

Section 2: Financial Motivation

Is your salary sufficient to meet your financial needs?

- Yes, completely
- Somewhat sufficient
- Somewhat insufficient
- No, completely insufficient

Which financial incentives are most important to you? (*Select up to 3*)

- Salary increase
- Performance-based bonuses
- Grants and research funding
- Additional payments for teaching workload
- Financial support for conferences and travel
- Other (please specify)

How satisfied are you with the financial incentive system at your university?

(*Scale: 1 = Very dissatisfied, 5 = Very satisfied*)

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Does your university offer performance-based financial rewards (e.g., bonuses for research, teaching excellence)?

- Yes, regularly
- Occasionally
- No

Section 3: Career Growth and Professional Development

What factors are most important for your career growth? (*Select up to 3*)

- Opportunities for professional development
- Participation in international projects
- Earning academic degrees and titles
- Promotion to administrative roles
- Research collaborations and publications
- Other (please specify)

Does your university support your professional development (e.g., funding for courses, internships, or research grants)?

- Yes, fully
- Partially
- No

How important is participation in scientific conferences and publishing in prestigious journals to you?

- Very important
- Somewhat important
- Somewhat unimportant
- Not important

Do you feel that career advancement at your university is based on merit?

- Yes, completely
- Somewhat
- Not really
- No

What barriers do you face in achieving career growth? *(Select all that apply)*

- Limited opportunities for promotion
- Lack of institutional support
- High competition for positions
- Insufficient funding for research
- Lack of time due to teaching workload
- Other (please specify)

Section 4: Non-Financial and Social Motivation

Which non-financial incentives do you find most valuable? *(Select up to 3)*

- Recognition of achievements (awards, certificates)
- Flexible work schedule
- Comfortable working conditions
- Team-building and corporate events
- Access to mentorship and coaching programs
- Other (please specify)

Do you feel valued and supported by university leadership?

- Yes, completely
- Somewhat
- Not really
- No

Does your university encourage collaboration and teamwork among faculty members?

- Yes
- Somewhat
- No

How satisfied are you with the availability of research resources (labs, funding, databases)? (*Scale: 1 = Very dissatisfied, 5 = Very satisfied*)

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Do you feel you have a good work-life balance?

- Yes, completely
- Somewhat
- No, I often work overtime
- No, I feel constantly overworked

Does your university support mental health and well-being programs?

- Yes
- No

Section 5: Overall Motivation and Recommendations

On a scale of 1-10, how motivated do you feel in your current position? (*1 = Not*)

Rank the following motivation factors in order of importance

(*1 = Most Important, 5 = Least Important*):

- Salary and financial benefits
- Career growth and promotions
- Recognition and awards
- Work environment and team support
- Research opportunities and funding

What could improve your motivation for teaching? (*Open-ended question*)

What changes would you suggest to improve the motivation system at your university? (*Open-ended question*)

This questionnaire will help to identify key factors of teacher motivation and identify areas for its improvement.

This survey aims to identify key factors influencing faculty motivation and suggest strategies for its improvement.

Practical Recommendation Method

Based on the findings of this study, concrete recommendations have been developed to enhance university motivational policies. Key recommendations include:

- Implementing flexible incentive systems tailored to the individual needs of faculty members.
- Improving university social policies to enhance working conditions and faculty well-being.
- Actively promoting research and scientific activities through grant funding and performance-based bonuses.

Creating opportunities for professional growth, such as advanced training programs, career development initiatives, and participation in international academic projects.

This study provides a deeper understanding of faculty motivation and its impact on teaching quality. The proposed recommendations can be applied in higher education institutions to improve the efficiency of the educational process and enhance faculty job satisfaction.

RESULTS

A review of the literature provides valuable insights into effective approaches for increasing faculty motivation in universities. The analysis of previous studies has allowed for a systematic classification of various motivation strategies applied in higher education institutions (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Measures to Enhance Faculty Motivation in Higher Education

Motivations	Measures to increase motivation
1. Financial Motivation	<p>Competitive salary levels aligned with faculty qualifications and workload.</p> <p>Incentives for research achievements, including grants, academic publications, and earned titles or degrees.</p> <p>Bonuses and additional payments for seniority, program accreditation, and participation in research projects.</p> <p>Performance-based financial rewards for outstanding teaching and research contributions.</p> <p>Funding for professional development (e.g., conferences, training programs, study visits).</p>
Financial support of academic activities	<p>Internal university grants for young faculty members and doctoral researchers to encourage academic growth and research innovation.</p> <p>Partial reimbursement for transportation and meals, easing financial burdens and improving work conditions.</p> <p>Conference and publication funding to support faculty participation in national and international academic events</p>
Career Development and Professional Growth	<p>Opportunities for academic promotion and structured career advancement pathways</p> <p>Educational Programs for Experience Exchange (Faculty exchange programs with leading universities to promote cross-institutional collaboration and knowledge sharing; Joint academic projects that encourage interdisciplinary research and international cooperation; Workshops and training sessions led by experts to introduce best teaching and research practices; Sabbatical leave opportunities for faculty members to engage in advanced study, research, or professional development abroad.</p> <p>Regular training and professional development programs to enhance teaching and research skills.</p>
Access to scientific and educational resources	<p>Free access to databases and scientific literature</p> <p>Reduction of excessive administrative burdens, allowing faculty to focus on research and teaching</p>

TABLE 1. Continuación

Motivations	Measures to increase motivation
Comfortable Working Conditions	<p>Improvement of working conditions, including well-equipped research labs and modernized teaching spaces.</p> <p>Recognition programs (awards, honorary titles, certificates) for outstanding contributions.</p> <p>Modernized classrooms and research facilities equipped with up-to-date technology and resources.</p> <p>Well-maintained office spaces with adequate lighting, ventilation, and ergonomic furniture to enhance productivity.</p>
2. Non-Financial Motivation	<p>Recognition and awards – Acknowledgment of faculty achievements through certificates, honorary titles, and institutional awards.</p> <p>Access to professional development programs – Workshops, mentorship programs, and leadership training to enhance skills.</p> <p>Participation in decision-making – Involvement of faculty in university governance, strategic planning, and curriculum development.</p> <p>Workplace culture and psychological support – Fostering a positive and inclusive academic environment through teamwork, peer support, and mental well-being initiatives.</p>
3. Social Support	<p>Health and wellness programs – Access to medical insurance, psychological support, and well-being initiatives for faculty and their families.</p> <p>Retirement and pension benefits – Ensuring financial security through well-structured pension plans and social benefits.</p> <p>Team-building and corporate events – Organizing faculty retreats, cultural activities, and social gatherings to strengthen collegiality.</p> <p>Childcare and family support programs – Providing on-campus childcare facilities, parental leave policies, and family-friendly workplace initiatives.</p> <p>Housing and relocation assistance – Support for faculty in securing affordable housing or relocation subsidies for those moving to a new city.</p>
4. Intrinsic Motivation	<p>Sense of professional fulfillment – Encouraging faculty members to take pride in their teaching, research, and contributions to academic development.</p> <p>Opportunities for creative self-actualization – Providing autonomy in research topics, innovative teaching methods, and interdisciplinary projects</p> <p>Engagement in cutting-edge research – Allowing faculty to work on pioneering studies and collaborate with leading experts in their field.</p> <p>Intellectual challenge and personal growth – Offering stimulating academic environments where faculty can continuously learn and develop.</p> <p>Opportunities to mentor and inspire students – Creating rewarding teaching experiences where faculty can shape the next generation of professionals and researchers.</p>
5. Extrinsic Motivation	<p>External evaluation and feedback – Regular performance reviews with constructive feedback from peers, students, and administrators.</p> <p>Public acknowledgment and reputation – Opportunities to gain professional recognition through media, academic rankings, and institutional promotions.</p> <p>International exposure and collaborations – Invitations to prestigious conferences, faculty exchange programs, and global research partnerships.</p>

Source: compiled according to authors own research.

To ensure faculty motivation and job satisfaction, universities should implement a competitive salary structure that reflects the quality of professional responsibilities, faculty qualifications, and market competition for academic talent. Additionally, various financial incentives should be introduced, including bonuses for securing research grants, publishing scientific works, and earning academic titles and degrees.

A seniority-based bonus system could also be beneficial, rewarding faculty for long-term service, program accreditation efforts, and contributions to research project development. To further promote faculty engagement in academic publishing, universities should allocate dedicated budgetary resources for conference participation and publication in prestigious scientific journals.

Supporting early-career researchers is crucial. Establishing internal university grants specifically for young faculty members and doctoral researchers can encourage innovation and long-term commitment to academia. Additionally, institutions should consider partial reimbursement for faculty transportation expenses and meal subsidies for on-campus dining, improving overall work-life balance.

For effective career advancement, universities must create opportunities for faculty to obtain academic titles and degrees. One effective approach is to develop educational programs focused on experience exchange between senior and junior faculty members. Special emphasis should be placed on professional development initiatives, including retraining courses, internships, and skill enhancement programs. These should not only cover subject-specific expertise but also emphasize modern pedagogical innovations and teaching methodologies.

To support faculty research and teaching effectiveness, universities must ensure free access to academic databases, scientific literature, and other essential resources. Furthermore, streamlining administrative processes is essential—reducing bureaucratic barriers and optimizing university documentation systems can significantly enhance faculty efficiency in both teaching and research activities.

Finally, improving working conditions and social infrastructure is critical. Universities should invest in modernized classrooms, well-equipped research laboratories, and designated areas for faculty rest and meals, ensuring a comfortable and supportive environment for academic work.

By implementing these measures, universities can foster a motivating and productive environment that enhances faculty performance, professional development, and institutional competitiveness.

To strengthen non-financial motivation among university faculty, institutions should regularly organize corporate events and actively promote the achievements of their researchers in mass media, including online platforms. Recognizing faculty members who contribute significantly to the university's development is essential. Various official acknowledgment forms, such as faculty honor boards, should be utilized to highlight academic excellence and institutional contributions.

Ensuring social stability within the university community is equally important. Universities should provide legal and financial assistance to employees facing difficult life circumstances. Additionally, organizing sports and wellness programs for faculty and their families can significantly enhance workplace morale and well-being.

Internal faculty organizations, such as university unions, can also play a crucial role in supporting academic staff by advocating for better working conditions and career advancement opportu-

nities. To stimulate research activity, universities should develop faculty-level and institution-wide grant programs and establish structured opportunities for pedagogical experience exchange among educators.

To enhance the university's external reputation, faculty members should be encouraged to participate in international research programs and projects. This not only elevates the university's global standing but also fosters professional growth and collaboration.

Given economic constraints, universities should prioritize non-financial incentives, such as implementing flexible work schedules and fostering effective student feedback mechanisms to recognize and reward teaching excellence.

Survey Results on Faculty Motivation. A faculty motivation survey conducted at Uzhhorod National University and Bohdan Khmelnytsky Melitopol State University yielded the following results:

- 43% of respondents indicated that career growth and professional development are their primary motivation.
- 35% emphasized financial motivation as a key factor.
- 22% highlighted social and non-financial incentives as important elements of their motivation (Figure 3).

These findings underscore the necessity of a balanced approach that integrates both financial and non-financial motivational strategies to enhance faculty engagement, job satisfaction, and overall academic performance.

Figure 3. University Faculty Motivation for Professional Activities

Source: Compiled according to authors own research.

To enhance faculty motivation in universities, it is essential to implement effective incentive mechanisms that contribute to increased productivity, job satisfaction, and professional growth. These mechanisms should be strategically designed to foster both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, ensuring long-term faculty engagement and institutional success (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Effective incentive mechanisms for enhancing faculty productivity, job satisfaction, and professional growth

Source: compiled according to authors own research.

1. Financial Incentives. Competitive financial rewards play a crucial role in faculty motivation and retention. Universities should establish salary structures that align with faculty expertise, workload, and market trends, ensuring fair compensation. Performance-based bonuses can serve as an additional motivator, rewarding faculty for excellence in teaching, research, and contributions to institutional growth. Research grants and funding opportunities should be readily available to support faculty engagement in scholarly work, fostering innovation and increasing the university's research output.

2. Career Growth & Professional Development. A clear and well-defined career trajectory is essential for faculty motivation. Universities should establish transparent promotion pathways that recognize academic excellence and leadership contributions. Professional development should be encouraged through training workshops, skill enhancement programs, and certifications, allowing faculty to continuously improve their teaching and research methodologies. International collaboration and faculty exchange programs can provide exposure to diverse academic practices, promoting cross-border research partnerships. Additionally, leadership and administrative training should be available for faculty members interested in assuming management roles, fostering a new generation of academic leaders who contribute to institutional excellence.

3. Non-Financial Recognition & Work Environment. Beyond financial rewards, non-monetary incentives play a significant role in fostering faculty satisfaction. Universities should implement public recognition programs, such as "Faculty of the Year" awards, certificates of excellence, and institutional honors to acknowledge outstanding contributions. Flexible work schedules can help faculty maintain a healthy work-life balance, allowing them to engage in both teaching and research without excessive administrative burdens. Providing access to academic databases, digital tools, and well-equipped research facilities enables faculty to work more effectively and advance their scholarly pursuits. Additionally, reducing bureaucratic constraints and streamlining administrative processes can significantly enhance faculty productivity, allowing them to focus more on their core academic responsibilities.

4. **Social Support & Institutional Engagement.** A supportive university environment fosters long-term faculty commitment. Institutions should offer wellness programs that prioritize faculty health, including mental health support, fitness programs, and stress management workshops. On-campus childcare services and family-friendly policies can significantly improve work-life balance, making academia more accessible for faculty with families. Additionally, faculty associations and mentorship programs can create a sense of community and professional solidarity. Organizing team-building activities, faculty retreats, and social gatherings helps strengthen collegial relationships, fostering a collaborative and inclusive academic culture. Universities should also promote work-life balance initiatives, such as reasonable teaching loads, paid leave policies, and faculty well-being programs, ensuring a sustainable and supportive work environment.

5. **Research & Innovation Incentives.** Encouraging research and academic innovation is vital for institutional success. Universities should establish internal grant programs to fund faculty-led research projects, allowing scholars to explore new academic frontiers. Interdisciplinary collaboration should be actively promoted, enabling faculty members from different fields to work together on innovative projects. Providing financial support for conference participation and academic publications ensures that faculty can disseminate their research globally, enhancing the university's academic reputation. Additionally, investment in digital learning technologies, research software, and modern laboratory facilities allows faculty to leverage cutting-edge tools in their teaching and scholarly work. By creating an environment that fosters research excellence, universities can position themselves as leading academic institutions on a national and global scale.

Therefore, a comprehensive support system and a well-structured faculty motivation strategy can significantly enhance the quality of teaching and research activities within the university.

DISCUSSION

Faculty motivation in higher education is a crucial factor in enhancing the effectiveness and quality of professional responsibilities. It is primarily driven by two key forms of motivation: extrinsic and intrinsic motivation, each playing a distinct role in academic engagement. Extrinsic motivation is influenced by external rewards such as career advancement opportunities, financial incentives, and institutional recognition, while intrinsic motivation stems from personal fulfillment, intellectual curiosity, and the passion for teaching and research.

Among the most significant motivating factors for university faculty are engagement in scientific research, professional status in society, intellectual work, pedagogical activities, and the flexibility of academic schedules. These factors collectively contribute to faculty satisfaction, long-term commitment, and overall productivity.

Achieving an optimal level of motivation requires a comprehensive and synergistic approach, combining multiple motivation strategies to maximize their collective impact. A well-structured motivation system not only enhances faculty performance and job satisfaction but also leads to higher-quality educational services, reducing faculty turnover and encouraging continuous professional development and creative engagement. Ultimately, an effectively motivated faculty contributes to the institution's academic reputation, research output, and long-term success.

CONCLUSIONS

An effective faculty motivation system in universities requires a comprehensive and multifaceted approach, integrating financial, non-financial, and social incentives. Achieving a high level of faculty engagement is possible through a combination of diverse motivation strategies, tailored to meet the individual needs of academic staff. Implementing the proposed measures will enhance university competitiveness, reduce faculty turnover, and create favorable conditions for the professional growth of academic and research staff.

Beyond financial and structural incentives, a long-term motivation strategy must consider not only economic and social factors but also psychological aspects that influence job satisfaction. Supporting scientific initiatives, developing internal and external recognition mechanisms for achievements in education and research, and strengthening mentorship programs play a crucial role in fostering faculty engagement and career development.

Furthermore, establishing a continuous feedback loop between faculty and university administration is essential for identifying challenges early and adjusting motivational policies accordingly. In the context of modern higher education, digital transformation and the expansion of distance learning models require universities to develop additional motivation strategies that support faculty in adapting to new teaching technologies and methodologies.

Ultimately, a holistic improvement of faculty motivation systems will not only contribute to individual professional growth but also strengthen universities' positions in the global education landscape. Investing in faculty motivation is an investment in the quality of education, institutional reputation, and long-term academic excellence.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Tomashev'ska, I. (2023). Modelling management of motivation of professional activities for teachers in a pre-school education institution. *Bulletin of Alfred Nobel University Series Pedagogy and Psychology*. 1. 204-212. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.32342/2522-4115-2023-1-25-22>
- Altamirano, M. (2024). US higher education in crisis: A study of leadership challenges in a post-pandemic world. In *The Palgrave handbook of crisis leadership in higher education* (pp. 625-637). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Samborska, O., Savchuk, P. (2023). The Experience of Implementation of Elements of Dual Education in the Students' Pedagogical Practice of the Institution of Vocational Higher Education. *Problems of Education*. 262-279. <https://doi.org/10.52256/2710-3986.1-98.2023.17>.
- Rubia, J., Niere, Marvin Ian, Jortil, M. (2023). Transformational Leadership and Organizational Commitment of Selected Higher Education Institutions in Zamboanga Peninsula. *Sprink Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*. 2. 19-30. [10.55559/sjahss.v2i06.116](https://doi.org/10.55559/sjahss.v2i06.116).
- Urdabayev, M., Ainakul, N., Sabdenaliyev, B. (2024). Modernization of the Motivation Systems in Higher Education: Challenges and Digital Solutions. *Eurasian Journal of Economic and Business Studies*. 68. 111-126. <https://doi.org/10.47703/ejeb.v68i3.431>.
- Nzimande, Sindisiwe & Qwatekana, Zikho & Ndlovu, Thulile & Sithole, Nothando. (2023). Unravelling the link between academic staff tenure and motivation: Extended curriculum programme dilemma for staff retention. *Journal of Management & Administration*, 17(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/3.1-18.10.5281/zenodo.10036866>.

- Samko, Alla (2023). Analysis of the theoretical foundations of the self-educational activity of research and teaching staff of higher education institutions. *Bulletin of Luhansk Taras Shevchenko National University*. 7-14. [https://doi.org/10.12958/2227-2844-2023-5\(359\)-7-14](https://doi.org/10.12958/2227-2844-2023-5(359)-7-14).
- Tiwari, Puja & Chatterjee, Satakshi (2021). The effect of motivation on the individual productivity level of the teaching staff in private higher education institutions of west Bengal, India: a study. *Towards Excellence*, 13(3). 478-488. <https://doi.org/10.37867/TE130340>.
- Venkatesh, A. N., Krishna, S. H., Banu, S. R., Elamparuthi, D., Sharief, S., Bethapudi, A. (2023). Impact Of Job Enrichment on Work Motivation of Non-Teaching Staff in Private Higher Education Institutions of Punjab. *European Economic Letters (EEL)*, 13(4), 187–197. Retrieved from <https://www.eelet.org.uk/index.php/journal/article/view/559>
- Kerry, P., Amoozegar, A., Ardebilpour, M. (2023). Exploring the influence of knowledge sharing motivation and management support on knowledge sharing intention among academic staffs in Nigerian higher education institutions. *Seybold Report*. 18. 936-947. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/BDWQK>.
- Tabachuk, V. (2022). Main determinants of the motivation of staff of higher education institutions in modern conditions. *Actual Problems of Economics*. 1. 81-91. <https://doi.org/10.32752/1993-6788-2022-1-254-81-91>.
- Okaka, Wilson (2024). Communicating Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) Human Resource Management Effectiveness of Staff Motivation for Institutional Security. *9TH international interdisciplinary conference* 6th- 8th NOV, 2024